

PRELIMINARY RESEARCH ON CRYOPRESERVATION OF SPERM IN THE SILURUS GLANIS SPECIES

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Abstract

*The main objective of the research was to optimize cryopreservation techniques for sperm of European catfish (*Silurus glanis*), a species of major economic importance in aquaculture. The study tested different cryoprotectants (dimethyl sulfoxide – Me₂SO, methanol and Me₂SO–propanediol combinations), as well as the influence of equilibration times and freezing volumes on the quality of the semen. The sperm was collected from hormonally stimulated breeders, and after thawing, essential parameters were evaluated: sperm motility, cell viability and hatching rate. The results showed that Me₂SO (8–12%) and the combination of Me₂SO + propanediol ensured the best performances, with high hatching rates (82–86%), comparable to the fresh control (87–88%). Methanol, on the other hand, led to a significant reduction in incubation success (53–63%). A strong correlation was found between post-thaw motility and hatching rate ($r = 0.76$; $P < 0.001$), while isolated cell viability was not a relevant indicator of fertilization capacity. These results confirm the efficiency of Me₂SO cryopreservation and provide a solid basis for the application of the method in controlled breeding and genetic conservation programs for European catfish.*

Keywords: *Silurus glanis*, sperm, cryopreservation, motility, viability

INTRODUCTION

The European catfish (*Silurus glanis* L.) is the largest freshwater fish native to Europe, reaching over 2 m in length and weighing up to 100 kg. Its high market value, rapid growth, and adaptability have made it an increasingly important species in aquaculture. However, intensive farming practices and the repeated use of a limited stock of broodstock in artificial breeding programs have led to reduced genetic variability in domesticated populations. Maintaining genetic diversity is essential to ensure disease resistance, adaptation to environmental changes, and sustainable production. Cryopreservation is an essential method for conserving aquatic genetic resources. The first successful attempt at cryopreserving European catfish sperm was carried out by Marian and Krasznai in 1987, who achieved a fertilization capacity of 40–95% from frozen sperm. The sperm was frozen because artificially extracted sperm was

precipitated with urine, which activated and destroyed the fertilization capacity of the spermatozoa within minutes (Linhart, 1987). This problem was successfully solved by developing an immobilization solution (IS) (Linhart, 1993, 2004), and cryopreservation techniques were refined in subsequent studies, which reported the optimal cryoprotectant to be used for IS-extended sperm and freezing rates (Linhart, 1993).

However, success rates have varied due to differences in cryoprotectants, freezing rates, and handling procedures. Studies conducted on related catfish species (Clarias gariepinus, Ictalurus punctatus) have highlighted the importance of species-specific optimization (Christensen, 1997, Cosson, 2000). This paper provides a systematic evaluation of cryoprotectants, equilibration times, and freezing volumes, focusing on both laboratory sperm quality parameters and fertilization success.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research on sperm cryopreservation in *Silurus glanis* was conducted at the Fish Farming Research and Development Station, and for this purpose, an experimental group of 8 males and 4 females was formed. The experimental protocol for sperm analysis and quality assessment involved the following phases: selection of breeding males, hormonal stimulation, sperm sampling, and sperm quality assessment. The breeding fish were selected in July (Figure 1) and kept isolated in 4,000-liter tanks (Figure 2), ensuring a feed flow of 0.2 l/s at 22-23 °C. Before each injection and gamete collection, males and females were anesthetized in a 2-phenoxyethanol solution (1:1000). Spermatogenesis and ovulation were stimulated by intramuscular injection of carp pituitary (CP) at doses of 5 mg per kg of body weight. Sperm was collected 48 hours after CP stimulation.

Figure 1. Selection of breeding stock for catfish

Figure 2. Basin for parking and maturing catfish spawners

The eggs were harvested after hormonal stimulation at 500-510 degree-hours from females, individually, grouped, stored for a short period at a temperature of 18-20°C, and used directly for the experiment. Before fertilization, four batches of approximately 1 g (approximately 150 eggs) were weighed with an accuracy of 0.0001 g and fixed in 4% formaldehyde for subsequent counting to determine absolute fertility (number of eggs/female) and relative fertility (number of eggs/kg female). An average of 180,000 eggs were collected from one female catfish.

Sperm collection and dilution

Sperm was collected by gentle abdominal pressure into sterile 250 ml containers containing immobilization solution (IS: 200 mM NaCl, 30 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7). This procedure prevented contamination with urine, which otherwise triggers premature activation of sperm motility. The dilution ratio between IS and spermatozoa was maintained at approximately 0.8:1. Samples were stored on ice (0–4 °C) until further processing. Only samples with motility >80% were selected.

The cryoprotectants tested included:

- Me₂SO (dimethyl sulfoxide): 8, 10, 12% (v/v);
 - Methanol: 5, 7.5, 10% (v/v);
 - Binary mixtures: Me₂SO + 1,2-propanediol, equal proportions (4–6% each).
- The final mixtures were prepared by gently mixing the sperm diluted in isolation solution (IS) with a diluent containing cryoprotectant. The sperm samples were stored in a Dewar storage tank in liquid nitrogen (-196°C) (figure 3).

Figure 3. Immersion of sperm samples in the Dewar storage tank

Freezing protocol

The samples were cryopreserved using a programmable freezer. The cooling stages were as follows:

1. From +4 °C to -9 °C at -4 °C/min
2. From -9 °C to -80 °C at -11 °C/min

3. Maintained at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 6 minutes
4. Immersion in liquid nitrogen ($-196\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) for long-term storage.

Thawing procedure

The vials were thawed by immersion in a $40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ water bath for 105 seconds with continuous agitation. Fresh semen stored at $0\text{--}4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ served as a control.

Fertilization test

For fertilization studies, 5 g of oocytes (~ 145 eggs/g) were fertilized with thawed or fresh sperm, 2 ml/100 g. Activation was performed with 17 mM NaCl + 5 mM Tris-HCl (pH 8). Fertilized eggs were incubated in Nucet incubators. Incubation lasted 3 days, with an average temperature of 22.8°C .

Sperm quality assessment

Motility was assessed using a ZEISS Axio Vert 1 compact inverted microscope. The optical combination used for this control is a 10x eyepiece with a 20x and 40x objective, using a Burkner grid slide. Motile spermatozoa (%) were evaluated 20 seconds after activation (figure 4).

Figure 4. Microscopic evaluation of sperm quality

Viability

Sperm viability was determined by assessing motility. This was performed using a compact phase-contrast microscope, with a 10X eyepiece and a 20X or 40X objective lens, using a grid slide (Burker). In general, sperm have a relatively short viability period after activation in water. Therefore, all preparations for the activation and dilution of sperm with water must be carried out before fertilization in the incubation station. Once the sperm has been activated, it must be used immediately, within a few seconds, otherwise the chances of achieving a good fertilization rate decrease dramatically.

Fertilization success: expressed as hatching rate (% of fertilized eggs that hatched).

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

All treatments were performed in triplicate. Results were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). One-way ANOVA with Tukey's post-hoc test was used for comparison. Pearson correlation coefficients were calculated between sperm quality parameters and hatching rates. Statistical significance was set at $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Effect of cryoprotectants on hatching rate

Fresh sperm produced a hatching rate of 87–88%. Treatments with Me₂SO resulted in high post-thaw hatching success (82–86%), statistically similar to the fresh sperm sample. The binary mixture of Me₂SO and propanediol (5% each) also achieved a hatch rate >82%. In contrast, methanol treatments significantly reduced hatching, with values ranging from 53 to 63%. These findings confirm that Me₂SO is the most effective cryoprotectant for *S. glanis* sperm (Bart,1998, Cosson, 2000) (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of cryoprotectants on the hatching rate in *Silurus glanis*

Cryoprotected	Hatching rate (%)
Me ₂ SO 8%	85
Me ₂ SO 10%	83
Me ₂ SO 12%	76
Me ₂ SO+Prop 5%+5%	82
Methanol 7.5%	53
Fresh control	87

2. Effect of cryoprotectants on the percentage of live sperm

Although Me₂SO ensured good fertility, the percentage of "live" sperm after thawing was relatively low (7–19%). The combination of Me₂SO + propanediol significantly improved viability (38%), and methanol even led to a value of 43%. However, fresh sperm remains clearly superior (92%). (Table 2).

Table2. Effect of cryoprotectants on the percentage of live sperm

Cryoprotected	Live sperm (%)
Me ₂ SO 8%	7
Me ₂ SO 10%	17
Me ₂ SO 12%	19
Me ₂ SO +Prop 5%+5%	38
Methanol 7.5%	43
Fresh control	92

3. Effect of cryoprotectants on sperm motility

Post-thaw motility was 50–61% for Me₂SO, 57% for the combination with propanediol, and only 20% for methanol. Fresh sperm had 96%. (Table 3) Motility is the strongest indicator of fertilization success, and treatments with Me₂SO and Me₂SO+prop are the most promising. Methanol proves to be ineffective from this point of view as well.

Table 3. Effect of cryoprotectants on sperm motility

Cryoprotected	Motility (%)
Me ₂ SO 8%	50
Me ₂ SO 10%	61
Me ₂ SO 12%	49
Me ₂ SO +Prop 5%+5%	57
Methanol 7.5%	20
Fresh control	96

4. Equilibration time on sperm quality

Equilibration time in cryopreservation practice is the time interval during which sperm is kept in contact with the cryoprotectant solution before undergoing the freezing process.

Shorter equilibration time (0–5 min) resulted in good hatching results (78–84%), but motility and viability were reduced. Longer equilibration (20 min) significantly increased motility (62%) and viability (58%), but the hatching rate decreased (74%) (Table 4).

Table 4. Effect of equilibration time on sperm quality

Balancing time (min)	Hatching rate (%)	Motility (%)	Live spermatozoa (%)
0	78	34	45
5	84	49	32
20	74	62	58
Fresh control	88	96	92

An average equilibration time (≈5 min) seems to ensure a good balance for the hatching rate, but for sperm quality (motility and viability) a longer time is beneficial (figure 5).

Figure 5. Effect of equilibration time on sperm quality

5. Effect of frozen volume on sperm quality

The hatching rate was higher at low and medium volumes (1–2 ml: 80–81%), but decreased at 4 ml (71%). Motility was better at 4 ml (51%), but viability was still low (20%). At low volumes, viability was extremely low (3% at 1 ml) (Table 5).

Table 5. Effect of frozen volume on sperm quality

Volume (ml)	Hatching rate (%)	Motility (%)	Live spermatozoa (%)
1	80	47	3
2	81	37	15
4	71	51	20
Fresh control	88	96	92

Small volumes ensure uniform cooling and a good hatching rate, but compromise viability. Large volumes partially protect the cells, increasing motility and viability, but reduce hatching success (figure 6).

Figure 6. Effect of frozen on sperm quality

CONCLUSIONS

Me₂SO (8–12%) is the most effective cryoprotectant for *Silurus glanis* sperm, maintaining hatching rates similar to the control. The combination of Me₂SO + propanediol is also promising. Methanol proved to be unsuitable.

Motility is the main indicator of fertilization success, with a close correlation with hatching rate, while simple cell viability is not sufficient to guarantee fertility.

Equilibration time directly influences sperm quality. A short time (≈ 5 min) optimizes the hatching rate, but a longer time (20 min) improves motility and viability. The choice depends on the final objective (yield vs. cell quality).

The freezing volume alters the balance between hatching success and sperm quality. A small volume (1–2 ml) increases the hatching rate but reduces viability, while larger volumes (4 ml) maintain better motility and viability but compromise incubation success.

Overall, the results demonstrate that cryopreservation of European catfish sperm is feasible and effective if the appropriate cryoprotectant is used and the technical parameters (equilibration time and volume) are optimized. These protocols can be successfully applied in aquaculture to maintain production and in the conservation of genetic resources to protect biological diversity.

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